

WHO IS A SOLICITOR, A BARRISTER AND A LAWYER

Rahmatova Umidakhon Mirzaolimovna

Fergana school of law

English teacher for lawyers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7294082>

ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the final phase of a three-year study into the role of lawyers in the development of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) following the implementation of the Civil Procedure Rules in 1999 and draws comparisons between US and Canadian studies. The paper centres on the use of mediation, which is recognised as the pre-eminent ADR process in the UK.' Data are analysed from 30 interviews with specialist commercial and construction-related lawyers who have utilised mediation in the dispute resolution process. Interviewees were selected from respondents to a national survey of lawyers specialising in commercial and construction-related practice. Whereas reaching settlement is typically regarded as the measure of success, this research focuses on other "mediation outcomes" experienced by solicitors and barristers, the majority of whom are repeat-users of the process. The data reveal that achieving settlement in a timely and cost-effective manner is among the chief advantages mediation has over litigation, but a number of other benefits can make the process an eligible option in dispute resolution. In particular, the process of mediation allows the parties to focus on or narrow the issues in dispute. Lawyerinterviewees also report tactical advantages from engaging in mediation. These range from providing the opportunity to examine the strengths and weaknesses of the case to testing witnesses and evidence. The data suggest lawyers are developing new practices in mediation, such as proposing the process in order to provide proof to the courts of willingness to compromise or participating in mediation in order to send messages to the opposition. Mediator-interviewees report a trend in mediation where cases are more difficult to settle and the participants more cognisant of mediation tactics.

Keywords: solicitor, barrister, lawyer, advocates, lawyer-client, audience, commpn laws, fusion.

INTRODUCTION

At the present time, lawyers in England are divided into two distinct groups, barristers and solicitors.l Theoretically barristers are advocates and specialists in various fields of law, and solicitors are lawyers who deal with clients directly employing barristers for advice and advocacy in higher courts. Solicitors are classically called men of affairs who advise the public in legal and business

matters. Barristers are not authorized to initiate lawyer-client relations and must wait for work from solicitor. In 1987, these theoretical conclusions are only partially true. More clients are represented in courts by solicitors than by barristers, though solicitors only have a right of audience in the lower courts. Barristers do a large amount of advisory and drafting work that has nothing to do with litigation. Some barristers are specialists while many are what are called general common law lawyers. Many solicitors specialize in various fields of law, and some are as specialized as any barrister. Journalists have commented about the seeming anomalies involving the English legal profession. The Economist of London said in 1983 that: The original reasons for dividing lawyers into two categories - barristers and solicitors - have long since disappeared, but the distinction remains. In theory the 4,800 barristers are supposed to be the specialists in advocacy or in particular areas of the law. The 44,000 solicitors are, often misleadingly, described as the general practitioners. In fact, some barristers are not specialists, some solicitors are. Some solicitors are better advocates than many barrister. Although there has been continuous agitation for granting solicitors greater rights of audience, the clamor for outright unification of the legal profession and the discarding of any distinction between barristers and solicitors, i.e., "fusion," has recently been given impetus by official recommendations from the solicitors body, The Law Society.

FACTS

The solicitor⁷ was convicted in February 1998 on four counts of aggravated indecent assault involving his stepchildren, which occurred during April and May 1997. He was initially sentenced to three months' imprisonment. However, on appeal the sentence was fully suspended after the solicitor agreed to enter a three year good behaviour bond. The Law Society of New South Wales then initiated disciplinary action against him in the Administrative Decisions Tribunal, arguing that he was unfit to practise. Those disciplinary proceedings were dismissed by the Tribunal in October 2000, because the Law Society had failed to give the solicitor written advice as to the outcome of its investigation. ⁸ Correspondence then ensued between the Law Society and the solicitor to determine whether it would bring fresh proceedings against him. In May 2000, the solicitor was charged with further offences, of which he was convicted on 7 November 2000,⁹ but the Law Society remained unaware of this until informed by the solicitor in August 2001. The Law Society then commenced proceedings before the New South Wales Court of Appeal, invoking that Court's inherent jurisdiction to discipline legal practitioners.

PROCEEDINGS IN THE COURT OF APPEAL

While the statutory power to remove a practitioner from the roll requires a preliminary finding of professional misconduct or unsatisfactory professional conduct, the Supreme Court has the inherent power to remove a lawyer from practice merely on the basis that he or she is no longer fit to practise.¹³ Nevertheless, both the Court of Appeal and the High Court chose to consider the issue of professional misconduct. The Court of Appeal found that, although the indecent assaults in April and May 1997 did not occur in the course of the solicitor's practice, such conduct did amount to professional misconduct because it led to his conviction on four counts of a serious crime¹⁴ involving serious breaches of the trust of his stepchildren and thus cast doubt on his inherent qualities and character. The Court thought that, like his stepchildren, vulnerable and unprotected clients must also be able to trust lawyers. IS Further, the court found that the failure to disclose the later charges, conviction and sentence also amounted to professional misconduct, as such matters were clearly relevant to the Law Society's investigation and the solicitor either deliberately withheld relevant information from the Law Society¹⁶ or failed to comprehend his duty of candour. That the conviction was later overturned on appeal was of no consequence. 18 The Court of Appeal ordered that the solicitor's name be removed from the roll of legal practitioners. His conduct in 1997 and failure to disclose the November 2000 convictions demonstrated that he lacked the character and trustworthiness required of a lawyer and therefore was not a fit and proper person to practise. The solicitor then appealed to the High Court.

CONCLUSIONS

The words of Brooke J in the Court of Appeal in *Dunnett v. Railtrack* (2002) are destined to become amongst the most-quoted from the growing corpus of case law relating to ADR: "skilled mediators are now able to achieve results satisfactory to both parties which are quite beyond the power of lawyers and court to achieve., 2 1 3 They are no doubt warmly welcomed by mediators as official validation of their contribution to dispute resolution. But in one respect they may do a disservice to the cause of mediation. More significantly for the purposes of this research, they may do a disservice to the understanding of mediation. This is because they are exclusively focused on success, defined by reference to the achievement of a settlement: "It may well be that the mediator is able to achieve a result by which the parties shake hands and feel that they have gone away having settled the dispute on terms with which they are happy

to live." No criticism of the Court of Appeal is intended in making this observation. It is entirely consistent with the usual view of the benefit of mediation. Judges might be expected to be concerned with settlement as the indicator of "success," since that is the outcome which removes the problem from their hearing list, with the added satisfaction that it was achieved by consensus, ADR providers also tend to place great emphasis on this outcome and settlement rates form an important part of their marketing, nor is it surprising that researchers, too, seek to measure their settlement rates, given the natural preoccupation of the principal actors in the process. But this preoccupation can result in insufficient (or no) emphasis being given to other outcomes. US commentators in particular use other criteria than outcome of mediation e.g. "user satisfaction," "efficiency improvement" and "improvements in the post-dispute climate." ° At the heart of the research reported in this article is a desire to appraise the potential benefits identified by users of mediation beyond the basic prospect of settlement. * Tactical outcomes. This is at once an important additional benefit and a potential weakness. The research examined the tactical effects of mediations referred to by a majority of interviewees, as "feeling the financial muscle" of the other side or permitting the parties to "eyeball" each other. A "test run" of the case is seen as a useful by-product of a mediation failing to achieve settlement. However, it is in the area of tactical outcomes that evidence emerged which is potentially damaging to the cause of mediation and, perhaps even more worryingly, to the reformed civil justice system. Put crudely, the availability of tactical advantage to parties may be seen as an attraction of mediation, but it also constitutes an invitation to their legal advisers to compete for it. There were indications that this is happening. Words like "manipulation," "squeeze," "bluff," "force" and expressions like "tactical games" and "defend the line" will be familiar to lawyers routinely engaged in litigation or arbitration. They may appear as anathema to committed mediators and equally may have an ominous ring for the success of the Woolf reforms to the civil justice system. Judges may feel, with some justification, that they have given ADR what support they can when the opportunities arise. The expectation, to put it no more strongly, that parties will actively explore the benefits of mediation, has been expressed in forthright terms even in those extreme cases where, exceptionally, refusal to mediate was permitted. Where necessary, judges have enforced the expectation by sanction, basically through costs. It is, therefore, an irony that the research identified reported instances of "costs terrorism" and other forms of tactical manoeuvring using the judicial statements in support of ADR in attempts

to secure advantage far removed from the spirit of mediation or of CPR. It is the overall conclusion of this research that a proper appraisal of the effects of mediation should include outcomes which cannot be understood by reference to a settlement rate and that evidence has been presented of the nature of those outcomes. Generally, these can be regarded as incidental, but not insignificant additional benefits of mediation, which may accrue even when no settlement is reached. However, the search for tactical advantage, ironically given the weapon of judicial support, is an outcome that may be hard to reconcile with the aims of the reformed civil justice system.

References:

1. P. Brooker and A. Lavers, Issues in the Development of ADR for Commercial and Construction Disputes, 19 CIV. JUST. Q. 353, 353-70 (2000)
2. S. Roberts, Mediation in the Lawyers' Embrace 55 MOD. L. REV. 258 (1992); S. Roberts, ADR and Civil Justice: An Unresolved Relationship (1993) 56 MOD. L. REV. 452; P. Robertshaw & J. Segal, The Milking of ADR, 12 Civ. Just. Q. 23 (1993).
3. M. X. Dustova. Improving the Mechanism of Financial Lending to Agricultural Enterprises //EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE. <https://emjms.academicjournal.io/index.php/> Volume:4, 2022.
4. M. X. Dustova. "Классификация Сельскохозяйственных Рисков" //Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance, Vol. 3 No.04 (2022): CAJITMF
5. M. X. Dustova. THE ROLE OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMY // SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS (Маҳаллий импакт факторли журнали), VOLUME 3, 2022 year.
6. M. X. Dustova. Tijorat banklarining kredit operatsiyalari va ular hisobini tashkil etish. International Conference on Innovation in Applied Sciences, Education and Humanities, hosted online from Barselona, Spain on July 31st 2022, pages 101-103
7. M. X. Dustova. Tijorat banklarida kredit risklarini samarali boshqarish. 4th -International Conference on Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education Hosted from Berlin, Germany <https://conferencea.org> July 30th 2022, pages 119-121

